

Reductive Alkylation of 2-Methyl-1,4-Naphthaquinone (Menadione) at Mercury Pool Cathode ϕ

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The electrochemical reduction of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone (I) dimethyl formamide (DMF) in presence of alkylating agents (organic halides) and different supporting electrolytes, leads mainly to the formation of 1,4-dialkyl ethers of naphthalene—the O-alkylated products. The reductive alkylation with ethyl bromide as alkylating agent, however, affords oxygen as well as carbon alkylated products, the higher yield of C-alkylation has been observed using LiCl as supporting electrolyte. Polarization, polarographic and cyclic voltammetric studies of (I) have been made and a plausible mechanism for ether formation has been suggested.

2-METHYL-1,4-NAPHTHAQUINONE (I) is related to vitamin K and is a biologically active substance. Mann and Barnes have briefly reviewed¹ the general electrochemistry of quinones. Fujinaga *et al*² have studied the electrochemical reduction of naphthaquinones in various aprotic solvents. Quinones with high redox potentials have been reductively methylated with dimethyl sulphate in the presence of pyridine³. The selective methylation of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinol to 2-methyl-1,4-dimethoxy naphthalene has been reported by Clinton *et al*⁴, employing usual chemical method. Anodic methoxylation of naphthalene as well as 1- and 2-methoxynaphthalene has also been reported by Bockmair and coworkers⁵. Two-one electron polarographic reduction of a number of quinones in aprotic media have been determined by Peover *et al*^{6,7}. Recently there have been great synthetic interest on the electrochemical reductive alkylation of a number of diketones⁸ and quinones⁹. In the present communication we describe the electrochemical reductive alkylation of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone in DMF at mercury pool cathode. Tetrabutyl ammonium bromide (TBAB) and lithium chloride have been used as supporting electrolyte.

Experimental

Materials: 2-Methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone, m.p. 106° (Sigma); lithium chloride (Sisco); ethyl bromide (Riedal); benzyl chloride (SDS) were used without further purification. Phenacyl bromide¹⁰ and tetrabutyl ammonium bromide¹¹ were prepared by reported methods.

Cell assembly: A 500 ml beaker with provision to hold porous diaphragm, thermometer and magnetic stirrer was used. Mercury pool was used as a cathode (area 55.89 cm²) and carbon plate inside the diaphragm served as anode. Polarization studies were made with reference to saturated calomel electrode.

Electrolysis and work up: Following is the detail of a typical electrolysis. Catholyte: 120 ml 2% lithium chloride or TBAB solution in DMF containing 2 g of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone and organic halide in 1:2 molar ratio respectively. Anolyte: 50 ml 2% lithium chloride or TBAB solution in DMF. Details of the experiment are given in Table 1. The current was passed for theoretical time corresponding to 2F/mole. During electrolysis, the catholyte assumed a dark brownish green colour which persisted even at the end of the electrolysis. The catholyte was filtered off and DMF was stripped off at 50°/35 mm. The content was poured into distilled water and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered off and the solvent was removed by distillation. The residue was chromatographed on a column of silica gel. Elution with different solvents or solvent mixture gave corresponding 1,4-diethers of 2-methyl naphthalene.

In case of the reaction with ethyl bromide, two products were obtained. The first product (IIa), a colourless solid, was isolated by eluting silica gel column with pure petroleum ether (60-80°) and petroleum ether-benzene (4:1) mixture, while the second product (III), an orange coloured solid, was obtained by eluting with petroleum ether and benzene (1:1) mixture. The yield, m.p. and spectral data of the products obtained are given in Table 2.

Polarographic and cyclic voltammetric study: A solution (10⁻⁴ molar) of (I) in dry DMF containing 0.1 molar tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (dried) was used for polarographic (Fig. 1) and cyclic voltammetric (Fig. 2) studies. Polarographic study was carried out in a three electrode system cell (Pt being counter electrode) and reduction potential was measured with reference to saturated calomel electrode. Cyclic voltammetry was carried out in

ϕ Dedicated to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra, my teacher, on the occasion of his 60th birthday.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS OF REDUCTIVE ALKYLATION OF 2-METHYL-1,4-NAPHTHAQUINONE (2.0 g) IN DMF AT MERCURY POOL CATHODE (area 55.89 cm², c.d. 0.0053 A cm⁻²) TEMPERATURE 20-25°

Sl. No.	Alkylating agent (wt. in g)	Supporting electrolyte (%)	Anode	Current (A)	Cell voltage (V)	Current efficiency (%)
1.	C ₂ H ₅ Br (2.51)	lithium chloride (2)	Carbon plate	0.3	18	30 ⁺
2.	C ₂ H ₅ Br (2.51)	tetrabutyl ammonium bromide (2)	Carbon plate	0.3	56-40	30 ⁺
3.	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ Cl (1.46)	tetrabutyl ammonium bromide (2)	Carbon plate	0.3	10	30.8
4.	C ₆ H ₅ COOH ₂ Br (2.3)	lithium chloride (2)	Carbon plate	0.3	24	38.0

† Total current efficiency for the compound IIa and III.

TABLE 2—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTIC OF PRODUCTS IN THE REDUCTIVE ALKYLATION OF 2-METHYL-1,4-NAPHTHAQUINONE

Alkylating agent (Supporting electrolyte)	Product ⁺ (Nature)	m.p. °C	Mass yield (%)	Characteristic ir bands (cm ⁻¹)		¹ H _{NMR} δ(ppm)
				C-H	C-O-C/>C=O	
EtBr (LiCl)	II _a (Colourless solid)	61	35	2820, 2880	1250, 1065	1.3-1.7(t)6H CH ₂ ; 2.4-2.5(s) 3H Ar CH ₃ ; 3.8-4.4(q)4H CH ₂ ; 6.6-8.8(m)5H Ar.
	III ^φ (Orange solid)	272-273	42	—	/1660	1.5-1.6(t)3H CH ₂ ; 1.7-1.8(t) 3H Ar CH ₂ ; 4.3-4.4(o)2H CH ₂ ; 7.3-8.5(m)4H Ar.
EtBr (TBAB)	II _a (Colourless solid)	61	57	2820, 2880	1250, 1065	—
	III ^φ (Colourless solid)	272-273	18	—	/1660	—
PhCH ₂ Cl (TBAB)	II _b (Colourless solid)	235	49	—	—	2.1(s)3H Ar CH ₂ ; 3.2(s)4H CH ₂ ; 6.8-7.4 (m)15H Ar.
PhOOCH ₂ Br (LiCl)	II _c (Colourless solid)	180	52	2990, 3060	1240, 1075	2.0(s)3H Ar CH ₂ ; 2.7(s)4H CH ₂ ; 6.6-7.4(m)15H Ar.

† All compounds gave satisfactory carbon and hydrogen analysis (Coleman 33 Model)

φ Absorbs at λ_{max} 280 nm.

Fig. 1. A polarogram at DME 0.1M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate in DMF.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone (I) in DMF at scan rate 9 V/sec. (between 500-1400 mV).

the same solvent-supporting electrolyte system at a scan rate of 9 V/sec between 500-1400 mV and the signals were recorded photographically from a Tektronix oscilloscope.

Results and Discussion

The electrochemical reductive alkylation of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone proceeds smoothly at

mercury pool cathode in DMF containing lithium chloride or TBAB as supporting electrolyte. Yields of corresponding diethers varies between 35-57% (C. E. 15-38%). Half wave potential for the polarographic reduction of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone in DMF containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate used as a supporting electrolyte is consistent with a mechanism involving two-one electron steps (Fig. 1). The value of their first and second

half wave potentials are -717.5 mV (slope 85 mV) and -1300 mV (slope 58.3 mV) respectively. Both reduction steps appear to be reversible. It seems from the polarographic studies that in the solvent of low proton availability 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone undergoes two-one electron polarographic reduction. The cyclic voltammetry (Fig. 2) also reveals two-one electron reduction in a reversible step (56 mV).

In the preparative study, the cathodic reduction of I was carried out at constant current (0.3 A). Polarization curves (Fig. 3) showed that maximum depolarization occurred at current density, 0.0057 $A\ cm^{-2}$.

Fig. 3. Polarization studies for 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone (I) at mercury pool :

(a) DMF and 2% LiCl, (b) DMF, 2% LiCl and 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone, (c) DMF, 2% LiCl and 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone and ethyl bromide, (d) DMF, 2% TBAB, 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone and benzyl chloride and (e) DMF, 2% TBAB, 2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone and phenacyl bromide

The reductive alkylation of I (Scheme 1) affords mainly O-alkylated products (IIa-c). However, in case of the reaction with ethyl bromide, C-alkylated product (III) has also been isolated. While the diethers (IIa-c) are colourless compounds, the product III (C-alkylated) is bright orange coloured, indicative of retained quinonoid structure.

(R = C_2H_5 ,
 IIa R = C_2H_5 , -
 IIb R = $C_2H_5CH_2$, -
 IIc R = $C_2H_5COCH_3$, -

Scheme 1

The effect of supporting electrolyte on the product distribution II and III in the cathodic reduction of I with ethyl bromide is remarkable and is given below in Table 3.

The higher yield of C-alkylated product in presence of LiCl is in conformity with an early report⁸. With benzyl chloride and phenacyl

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTE ON THE PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION (IIa AND III). THE CURRENT DENSITY AND OTHER PARAMETERS OF ELECTROLYSIS REMAINING SAME

Sl. No	Supporting electrolyte	Product yield(%)	
		IIa	III
1.	LiCl	35	42
2.	TBAB	57	18

bromide as the alkylating agents, only the O-alkylated products (IIb and IIc respectively) were obtained. Compared to the conventional chemical methods^{1,2-14} the electrochemical procedure reported here is easy and smooth to afford the diethers IIa-c.

During electrolysis, the catholyte developed a dark brownish green colour which persisted even at the end of the reaction. This is indicative of a possible intermediary of an anionic species. Based on the voltammetric and preparative studies the formation of 2-methyl naphthalene-1,4-diethers could possibly be represented in the following manner (Scheme 2) :

Scheme 2

The C-alkylated products probably also originate from the common reaction intermediate, the anion radical IV.

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